

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Klco et al. *Phys. Rev. A* 107, 012415. Published 11 January 2023. p.3.
- [2] Roman Dwilewicz & Jan Minac. (2023). Values of the Riemann zeta function at integers.
- [3] *The Astrophysical Journal*, 723:803–811, 2010 November 1. p.805.
- [4] CODATA Internationally recommended 2018-values of the Fundamental Physical Constants.
- [5] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), *Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys.* 2022, 083C01 (2022). p.27-31.
- [6] M. Aker et al. Collaboration. arXiv:2207.06337v1 [nucl-ex] 13 Jul 2022, p.2.
- [7] R.L. Workman et al. (Particle Data Group), *Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys.* 2022, 083C01 (2022). p.480.
- [8] NuFIT 5.2 (2022)
- [9] B. Berenji et al. *Phys. Rev. D* 93, 045019. 16 February 2016, p16
- [10] M. Buschmann et al. Dark matter from axion strings with adaptive mesh refinement. *Nat Commun* 13, 1049 (2022), p1